

MODE OF MOVEMENT OF POTATO TUBERS IN THE CIRCULAR MOTION OF A CYLINDRICAL ELEVATOR

Norchaev D.R.

Dr of Technical Sciences, Senior Researcher,
Scientific Research Institute of Agricultural Mechanization
Uzbekistan (Yangiyul)

Egamov J.J.

Ph.D. student of Scientific Research Institute of Agricultural Mechanization
Uzbekistan (Yangiyul)

Abstract: This article is a part of the scientific work entitled "Energy-saving potato digger's sieving and stacking parameters justification", and the movement of the sifted amount in the cylindrical elevator is studied from a theoretical point of view .

Keywords: potato digger, cylindrical elevator, potato and soil mixture, rotary motion.

In a cylindrical elevator, the separation of potatoes and foreign substances contained in it depends on the operating modes of the elevator. Based on this, a mixture of potato tubers and soil is rolled we studied the modes of movement in the elevator.

When a cylindrical elevator located at a horizontal or inclined angle rotates, the following modes of movement of the potato and soil mixture inside it can be seen on the cross section [4; p. 12]:

- movement with wear. In this, the potato and soil mixture is periodically distributed from the open surface AB to the CD state (Fig. 1, a);

- circular motion. A mixture of potatoes and soil forms a circular closed contour (Fig. 1, b). In this case, the mixture of potatoes and soil moves in the form of a segment with a curved surface or in the form of freely flying particles (shown by a dotted line in Fig. 1, b);

In addition, the mixture of potatoes and soil can vibrate. In this, the potato and soil mixture rotates with the elevator, rises to a certain height, and then slides along the inner surface of the elevator and descends again, this situation is repeated periodically. This situation can happen when the potato-soil mixture reaches the elevator in a small amount and it rotates with a small angle speed, and when the coefficient of friction of the potato-soil mixture on the surface of the elevator is smaller than the coefficient of friction between the mixtures. In practice, the car rarely works in this mode. The movement of the floating mass with erosion is not observed much.

Figure 1. Schemes of movement of potato and soil mixture in a cylindrical elevator [4; p. 15]

In practice, a circular movement of the mixture is observed in a more cylindrical elevator. Let's look at this mode of action.

Usually, the angular velocity of the elevator in rotation is $(0.1-0.6) \omega_{kr}$ when equal to , this mode of action appears stable. Here, ω_{kr} is the critical angular velocity of the elevator, and the mixture of potatoes and soil moves together with the elevator. Critical angular velocity ω_{kr} to determine the value of, we consider the equilibrium condition of potato and soil mixture particles at points S and M on the cross section of the inner surface of the cylindrical elevator (Fig. 1, b)

– for point S

$$mg - fm\omega_{kp}^2 R = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad \omega_{kp} = \sqrt{\frac{g}{fR}} ; \quad (1)$$

– for point M

$$mg - m\omega_{kp}^2 R = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad \omega_{kp} = \sqrt{\frac{g}{R}} . \quad (2)$$

Theoretically, the critical value of the rotational speed of the cylindrical elevator is equal to the greater of the values calculated by the expressions given above.

In practice, expression (2) is used, if $R = 0.3$ m, then $\omega_{kr} = 5.7$ rad/s or $n_{kr} = 55$ r/min. So, when the number of revolutions of the cylindrical elevator is equal to $n = 5.5-33$ r/min, the movement of the mixture of potatoes and soil inside it is in the form of a circular movement.

Determining the filling coefficient of the potato tuber and soil mixture depending on the amount of transfer to the elevator

In one rotation of the cylindrical elevator, the amount that is placed between the adjacent steps of the screw guide installed inside it can be determined using the following expression:

$$V = \frac{2\pi Q}{\omega \rho} , \quad (3)$$

where Q is the amount of potato tuber and soil mixture transferred to the elevator, kg/s; ρ - density of potato soil mixture, kg/m³.

This quantity corresponds to the following area in the cross section of the cylindrical elevator:

$$S_a = \frac{V}{S_g}, \tag{4}$$

where s_b is the pitch of the screw guide, m.

The filling coefficient of the elevator, which depends on the cross-sectional surface of the potato and soil mixture inside the cylindrical elevator, is equal to:

$$q = \frac{S_a}{\pi R^2}. \tag{5}$$

Considering (3) and (4), (5) can be written as follows:

$$q = \frac{2Q}{\omega R^2 \rho s_g}. \tag{6}$$

In this expression, the angular velocity of the elevator is ω expressing by the number of revolutions n , depending on the number of revolutions and the pitch of the screw guide, a graph of the change of the filling coefficient of the elevator when $Q = 1/6$ kg/s was constructed (figures 2, a and b).

Figure 2. The influence of the number of revolutions of the cylinder (n) and the screw guide (s_v) on the elevator filling coefficient

From these graphs, we can see that the number of revolutions of the cylindrical elevator and the pitch of the screw guide are inversely proportional to the coefficient of filling, as the number of revolutions and the size of the screw pitch increase, causing the coefficient of filling to decrease.

On the other hand, this surface is also equal to the following [5; p. 48] (Fig.1,a):

$$S_a = \left(\frac{\pi \delta_0}{180} - \frac{\sin 2\delta_0}{2} \right) R^2, \quad (7)$$

Considering expressions (3) and (4), (7) can be written as:

$$\left(\frac{\pi \delta_0}{180} - \frac{\sin 2\delta_0}{2} \right) R^2 = \frac{2\pi Q}{\omega \rho s_a}. \quad (8)$$

This expression is solved using a numerical method, and the results are used in the process of scientific work.

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